

On the presence of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae) in Slovakia

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ABSTRACT: The presence of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) in Slovakia is reported. The European distribution of the species is summarised.

KEYWORDS: *Perillus bioculatus*, distribution, Slovakia, Europe.

Decades ago, the Nearctic bug species *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) was introduced to various European countries, among them Slovakia, as a biological pest control in attempts to control the invasive Colorado Potato Beetle *Leptinotarsa decemlineata* (Say, 1824) (Prasad & Pal, 2015; Kóbor & Brhane, 2024; van der Heyden et al., 2024).

So far, *P. bioculatus* has been reported as present in the following European countries: Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Kosovo, Moldova, North Macedonia, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Türkiye and

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Ukraine (Ćato et al., 2024; van der Heyden et al., 2024; Aukema, 2025). According to Kóbor & Brhane (2024), Slovakia is currently not inhabited by *P. bioculatus*.

Herein, the presence of *P. bioculatus* in Slovakia is reported: On 19.09.2025, an adult specimen (Fig. 1) was found in Hlohovec, located in the western part of the country (coordinates: 48.4228374014, 17.7931638509, accuracy: 42 m). Two photos of the specimen were uploaded to the online database iNaturalist (Bojnicanova, 2025).

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Figure 1. Specimen of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775), Hlohovec, Slovakia, 19.09.2025. (Photo: Eva Bojnicanova).

REFERENCES

- Aukema, B. (ed.), 2025, Catalogue of Palaearctic Heteroptera [Online database]. Available from: https://catpalhet.linnaeus.naturalis.nl/linnaeus_ng/app/views/introduction/topic.php?id=9&epi=1. (Accessed: 21.09.2025).
- Bojnicanova, E., 2025, Two-spotted Stink Bug (*Perillus bioculatus*). Photographs to be found on iNaturalist [Online database]. Available from: <https://www.inaturalist.org/observations/315355736>. (Accessed: 21.09.2025).
- Ćato, S., Doboš, M., Škugor, T., Pihlajamaa, O., Muradkhanyan, A., 2024, New data on the distribution of *Perillus bioculatus* (Heteroptera: Pentatomidae): first records from Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, North Macedonia, Georgia, and Armenia, *Acta Entomologica Serbica*, 29(2): 29-36.
- Kóbor, P., Brhane, D., 2024, Past, present and future of the two-spotted stink bug (*Perillus bioculatus*) in Europe revealed by citizen science, *Scientific Reports*, 14: 21494.
- Prasad, C.S., Pal, R., 2015, First record of two spotted stink bug, *Perillus bioculatus* (Fab.) from Meerut (U.P.) North India, *International Journal of Environmental & Agriculture Research*, 1(3): 9-11.
- van der Heyden, T., Morin, L., Dioli, P., 2024, First record of *Perillus bioculatus* (Fabricius, 1775) (Hemiptera: Heteroptera: Pentatomidae: Asopinae) in Italy, *Heteroptera Poloniae – Acta Faunistica*, 18: 35-37.